

Supplementary Document 1

Methodology and results of the system's evaluation in a simulation scenario

This document details the methodology and results obtained when evaluating the system proposed in the paper **Tablet-based Augmented Reality and 3D Printed Templates in fully guided Microtia Reconstruction: A clinical workflow**, in a simulation scenario. This work has been developed by Alberto Díez-Montiel, Alicia Pose-Díez-de-la-Lastra, Alba González-Álvarez, José I. Salmerón, Javier Pascau, and Santiago Ochandiano; and published in the journal *3D Printing in Medicine*.

Methodology

Before surgery, we evaluated the AR system in a simulation scenario that included the skull phantom, the PLA dental splint and the AR reference marker. The evaluation began by setting up the skull with the dental splint and the AR marker. Then, we initialized the AR application on the tablet and detected the AR marker to provide real-time visualization of the optimal ear position. Six biomedical engineers actively involved in surgical navigation research participated in the data acquisition process. Individually, they aligned the 3D printed ear with the corresponding virtual model using the AR application as guidance (**Figure 1**). The physical structure was securely affixed to the skull using playdoh.

Figure 1. Alignment of the real and virtual ears using the AR application in a simulation scenario.

Following each procedure, we captured 3D photographs of the ensemble with an Artec Eva structured light scanner (Artec3D, Senningerberg, Luxembourg). From them, we generated a 3D model and registered it to the ideal configuration using the iterative closest point (ICP) based surface matching technique. This process was conducted using the *model registration* module of SlicerIGT extension in 3D Slicer software (**Figure 2**) (1). The reference employed for registration was the surface of the skull biomodel (obtained from the CT scan of the head). Subsequently, we performed a morphometric analysis by measuring the Euclidean distance on each voxel of the reference surface to the closest point in the 3D model extracted from the surface scan. This analysis allowed us to assess the guidance accuracy provided by the AR application.

Figure 2. AR system evaluation steps after ear placement in the simulation scenario. (A) 3D scanning of the ensemble. (B) Image fusion performed by Artec Studio® software to reconstruct the 3D model. (C) 3D model visualization in 3D Slicer. (D) 3D model registration of the scanned object (green) and the reference ensemble (yellow) for further evaluation.

Results

Following the registration of the scanned models and the reference, we cropped the ear region in both structures, as it represents the primary area of interest in this work. **Figure 3** highlights any difference between both models considering Euclidean distances to homologous voxels. The reference model used to define positive or negative distances is the ideal plan with perfect ear positioning. Outliers were filtered out using a threshold set at the 95th percentile, since those large differences were due to scanning errors.

Figure 3. Morphometry analysis showing Euclidean distances between the ideal reference and the ears positioned by users 1 to 6 in the simulation scenario.

The mean absolute distance value obtained across all the experiments was 2.2 ± 1.7 mm, with a maximum distance of 7.3 mm observed in one of the cases. The same data is presented as a boxplot in **Figure 4**.

Figure 4. Euclidean distance of the ideal ear to the physical ear positioned on the simulation scenario, separated by user. Each box represents the first to third quartiles of the datasets. The median and the mean are indicated by the middle line and the white dot, respectively. The whiskers extend to the highest and lowest values, which are determined by ± 1.5 times the standard deviation.

References

1. SlicerIGT [Internet]. SlicerIGT; 2023 [cited 2023 Sep 8]. Available from: <https://github.com/SlicerIGT/SlicerIGT>